

Tropical plant genome sequencing is already underway in Brazil

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Abstract

Bedoya, Zapata and Sanín (2025) urge the inclusion of tropical plants in genome sequencing. We agree, emphasizing that this transformation is already underway in Brazil through coordinated, locally led initiatives delivering chromosome-scale assemblies. Aligned with the Earth BioGenome Project and the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework, these efforts build equitable collaborations and capacity, exemplifying how tropical plant genomics can advance from the Global South.

Main Text

Bedoya, Zapata, and Sanín¹ highlight a critical gap in plant genome sequencing: the underrepresentation of tropical species, despite their ecological, cultural, and global relevance. We agree, and emphasize that in Brazil—one of the world’s most megadiverse countries—tropical plant genomics is rapidly maturing, with coordinated, locally led efforts already producing high-quality, chromosome-scale assemblies.

Across universities (e.g., the CBioClima initiative²), state-owned companies and institutes (e.g., Embrapa and ICMBio), and private partners (e.g., Instituto Tecnológico Vale, through the GBB consortium³), groups are acting on these priorities: sequencing hyperdominant and endangered species from Amazonian forests and other biomes, alongside cultural keystones and crops that sustain biodiversity and local livelihoods. Most projects align with Earth BioGenome Project (EBP) recommendations⁴ and are led by Brazil-based teams; importantly, several are integrating genomic, ecological, physiological, and remote-sensing data to connect genes, traits, and ecosystem processes—exactly the translational arc the community needs.

These efforts also operationalize the Kunming–Montreal Global Biodiversity Framework (KMGBF) by generating genomic baselines and building regional capacity through equitable, locally anchored collaborations (Targets 4 and 20)^{5,6}, while addressing the historical pattern whereby tropical genomes were often sequenced outside their countries of origin⁷, and directly advance the call by Bedoya et al. for inclusive tropical genomics.

Momentum across Brazilian biomes

Examples across the major biomes illustrate this progress (Figure 1). Additionally, several Brazilian-led projects target non-native or model species, mostly agriculture-oriented with a focus on breeding and climate-change adaptation⁸. Notably, twenty-six ongoing projects on native taxa have already reached chromosome scale, which will more than triple the number of Brazilian-led tropical plant genomes. These projects span fruit trees and palms; morning glories, orchids and

bromeliads; hardwoods and medicinal plants; crops; forage grasses relevant to rangeland restoration; conifers and marine and freshwater algae. By linking genomic resources to traditional knowledge, local livelihoods, conservation, carbon storage, and climate resilience, these initiatives provide actionable tools to anticipate tropical biodiversity responses to rapid environmental change—moving beyond a strict “crop vs. non-crop” framing that poorly fits the tropics and extending the forum opened by Bedoya et al. Nonetheless, available reference genomes, and population-scale datasets still underrepresent biodiversity across Brazilian biomes (e.g., species native to the Pantanal wetlands remain unrepresented, despite taxa from other biomes).

Path forward

Advancing from here will require nationally coordinated programmes anchored in the Global South, clear access-and-benefit-sharing (ABS) arrangements, and sustained investment in people and infrastructure to ensure regional scientific leadership—imperatives that mirror updated EBP priorities on equitable partnerships, workforce development, and coordination at scale⁹. Tropical plant genomics in Brazil has matured into an established field, driving innovation and informing policy frameworks. A vibrant, locally led community is consolidating, capacity for long-term progress is being built, and many sequencing projects are nearing publication, advancing alignment with the KMGBF and the EBP. Endorsing and adequately resourcing Brazilian-led initiatives would directly advance the agenda articulated by Bedoya et al. and help accelerate delivery of a truly global, equitable reference library of tropical plant genomes.

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Competing interests

The authors declare no competing interests.

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Figure Legend

Figure 1. Tropical plant genome sequencing initiatives in Brazil. The map is stratified by biome, marking the primary biome of origin for each native species (a species may occur in multiple biomes, but only its primary biome is shown here) and highlighting only Brazilian-led initiatives and remaining gaps—reinforcing calls for coordinated funding, fair ABS, and local capacity building, as emphasized by Bedoya *et al.* An interactive version of the map is available at https://plantgenomics.ncc.unesp.br/Brazil_Plant_Genomes

